

Synthesis of Pyridopyrimidines and Quinolinopyrimidines

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Recently, we described novel synthesis of condensed pyrimidines^{1,2} and the biological evaluation of some of them². We wish to describe here the synthesis of pyridopyrimidines and quinolinopyrimidines with suitable functionalities for potential biological activity³⁻⁵. Reaction of uracil (2) with arylidenemalononitrile (1) in presence of piperidine afforded 2-amino-4-aryl-5,7-dioxopyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-3-carbonitriles (4a-c) in an essentially one-pot procedure. The formation of 4a-c is assumed to

material containing the suitably located functionality for direct conversion into the pyrimidine ring with suitable reagents. Thus, treatment of 4a-c with benzoyl isothiocyanate gave 1-amino-10-aryl-2-benzoyl-3-thioxopyrido[2,3-*d*]dipyrimidine-7,9-diones (6a-d). The reaction of 1 with equimolar quantities of 3 in the presence of piperidine gave hexahydroquinolines (8a-c) presumably via the acyclic structure 7. Treatment of 8a-c with benzoyl isothiocyanate effected the formation of pyrimidine ring and thus hexahydroquinolino[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (10) were obtained, which are assumed to be formed via intermediacy of thioureas (9). Compounds 4a-c and 10a-c have been tested against *Aspragillus niger*, *Bacillus subtilis* NRRL B 210, *Staphylococcus albus* and *Sarcina* using diffusion method. Compounds 4a-c and their condensed pyrimidines (10) showed no antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. albus* and *Sarcina* but showed a moderate activity against *A. niger* especially for those bearing chloro function.

proceed via initial Michael addition of 2 to 1 followed by cyclisation to dihydropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine intermediate (A), which subsequently underwent oxidation to fully aromatized 4. Enaminonitriles seemed to be a good starting

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer. Microanalysis was performed at Microanalytical unit, Cairo University and biological activity at Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Zagazig University. All new compounds gave satisfactory microanalytical data for C, H, N, S and Cl as appropriate.

7-Amino-5-aryl-6-cyano-1,2-dihydropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2,4-dione (4a-c): A solution of 2 (0.01 mol) and cyano-olefin (1; 0.02 mol) in DMF (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The mixture was then concentrated, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals: ν_{\max} 1 630–1 670 (CO), 2 218–2 222 (CN), 3 300–3 350 cm⁻¹; 4a, m.p. 417°, δ 7.2–7.4 (5H, m, ArH), 7.65 (2H, s, NH₂), 10.9 (1H, s, NH), 11.45 (1H, s, NH); 4b, m.p. 420°; 4c, 446°.

1-Amino-10-aryl-2-benzoyl-3-thioxopyrido[2,3-*d*]dipyrimidin-7,9-dione (6a-d): A mixture of benzoyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and 4 (0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals: ν_{\max} 1 640–1 680 (CO), 2 228/2 220 (CN) for 6c and 6d respectively, 3 300–3 500 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); 6a, m.p. 430°, δ 7.1–7.3 (5H, m, ArH), 8.1

(2H, br, NH₂), 10.0, 11.3 (each 1H, NH); **6b**, m.p. 448; **6c**, 458–60°.

2-Amino-4-aryl-3-cyano-1-phenyl-1,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-pyridin-5-ones (8a-e): A mixture of equimolar amounts (0.01 mol) of **3** and the appropriate cinnamionitrile (**1a-e**) was refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) in presence of catalytic amount of triethylamine (2 drops) for 1 h. The solid formed on standing, was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals: ν_{\max} 1 640–1 650 (CO), 2 210–2 230 (CN), 3 300–3 550 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); **8a**, mp. 200–01°, δ 1.9–2.0 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 2.1–2.3 (2H, m, CH₂), 4.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.7 (1H, s, 4H-pyridine), 6.8, 7.3, 7.6 (9H, m, ArH); **8b**, m.p. 222–24°; **8c**, 220–21°.

4-Amino-5-aryl-3-benzoyl-6-phenyl-2-thioxo-5,6,7,8,9,10-hexahydroquinolino[2,3-d]pyrimidine (10a-e): A mixture of benzoylthiocyanate (0.01 mol) and **8** (0.01 mol)

in dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals: ν_{\max} 1 670–1 680 (CO), 3 270–3 350 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); **10a**, m.p. 195°, δ 1.9–2.2 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 5.7 (1H, s, 4H-pyridine), 7.0 (2H, d, NH₂), 7.2–7.6 (15H, m, ArH); **10b**, m.p. 213–16°; **c**, 208–10°; **d**, 198–200°; **e**, 190°.

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